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“UNLOVING YOU”

We had our chance but all was ephemeral
We never lost the bind but I break your heart.

I've been lost astray but you remain there,
Patiently waiting even though you're tired
Sorry for hurting you and making you sad.

I'm a good girl gone mad,
I fancy you but I can't you don't deserve what I keep in my head

You're a nice guy everyone wanted,
With all the green flag that you are. Can't take the risk to ruin your life.

I wasn't joking when I said I love you